

INVESTIGAÇÃO DE DEFORMAÇÕES PERMANENTES EM COMPOSITOS
NANOMODIFICADOS APÓS A MOLDAGEM EM TEMPERATURAS ELEVADASINVESTIGATION OF PERMANENT STRAINS IN NANOMODIFIED COMPOSITES AFTER
MOLDING AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURESИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ОСТАТОЧНЫХ ДЕФОРМАЦИЙ В НАНОМОДИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ
КОМПОЗИТАХ ПОСЛЕ ФОРМОВАНИЯBABAYTSEV, Arseniy V.^{1*}; KUZNETSOVA, Ekaterina L.²; RABINSKIY, Lev N.³;
TUSHAVINA, Olga V.⁴;^{1,3} Moscow Aviation Institute (National Research University), Department of Engineering Graphics, 4
Volokolamskoe shosse, zip code 125993, Moscow – Russian Federation² Moscow Aviation Institute (National Research University), Institute of General Engineering Education,
Department of Perspective Materials and Technologies of Aerospace Designation, 4 Volokolamskoe shosse, zip
code 125993, Moscow – Russian Federation⁴ Moscow Aviation Institute (National Research University), Institute of Aerospace, Department of Managing
Exploitation of Space-Rocket Systems, 4 Volokolamskoe shosse, zip code 125993, Moscow – Russian
Federation* Correspondence author
e-mail: Ar77eny@gmail.com

Received 12 January 2020; received in revised form 14 November 2020; accepted 24 March 2020

RESUMO

Este trabalho investiga o efeito da nanomodificação do carbono no estado de tensão-deformação residual (ETD) após a moldagem. Uma das maneiras de reduzir tensões residuais e deformidades é a nanomodificação. O objetivo principal foi determinar o grau de influência dos parâmetros de nanomodificação no ETD residual. No âmbito deste estudo, foram feitas 4 placas. Duas placas foram feitas com um aglutinante convencional com assentamento [010/9010] e [010/4510] e duas placas com um material de ligação modificado com a mesma estrutura de camada. Para as placas fabricadas, as deformações foram medidas em cada um dos quatro lados, durante o qual foram obtidas deformações residuais nos painéis de fibra de carbono nano modificada para as camadas consideradas com e sem material de ligação modificado. Para analisar o estado de tensão-deformação residual, foi realizado um cálculo numérico e analítico. O cálculo numérico foi realizado pelo método dos elementos finitos para o caso em que a palca é fixada no ponto do centro geométrico, sem carga de energia, e a carga de temperatura é uma diferença de 100 °C. Um cálculo analítico foi realizado para o caso em que a placa está livre de fixação e carga de energia externa, e a carga de temperatura é uma diferença de 100 °C. Durante o estudo, variantes das propriedades físico-mecânicas da monocamada foram obtidas usando o *software* Digimat e o método de média de Mori-Tanaka. Os resultados obtidos pelos métodos analíticos e numéricos têm boa correlação entre si e, no decorrer da comparação com o experimento, foi determinado um método para calcular as características da monocamada mais próxima do resultado experimental. Com base nos resultados obtidos, foram tiradas conclusões sobre a possibilidade de reduzir ETD residual e a deformação em estruturas com esquemas de reforço assimétrico, utilizando uma matriz contendo nanopartículas de carbono.

Palavras-chave: *materiais compósitos, partículas de tamanho nano, nano modificação, deformações, deformidades residuais, tensões residuais, ETD.*

ABSTRACT

This work investigates the effect of carbon nanomodification on the residual stress-strain state (SSS) after molding. One of the ways to reduce residual stresses and deformities is nanomodification. The main objective was to determine the degree of influence of the nanomodification parameters on the residual SSS. Within the framework of this study, 4 slabs were made. Two slabs are made of a conventional binder with laying [0₁₀/90₁₀] and [0₁₀/45₁₀] and two slabs of a modified binding material with the same layer structure. For the fabricated plates,

deflections were measured on each of the four sides, during which residual strains were obtained in the panels of nanomodified carbon fiber for the considered layings with and without modified binding material. To analyze the residual stress-strain state, a numerical and analytical calculation was performed. The numerical calculation was carried out by means of the finite element method for the case when the slab is fixed at the point of the geometric center, with no power load, and the temperature load is a difference of 100 °C. An analytical calculation was carried out for the case when the slab is free from fastening and external power load, and the temperature load is a difference of 100°C. During the study, variants of the physicomechanical properties of the monolayer were obtained using the Digimat software and the Mori-Tanaka averaging method. The results obtained by analytical and numerical methods have a good correlation between each other, and in the course of comparison with the experiment, a method for calculating the characteristics of the monolayer that was closest to the experimental result was determined. On the basis of the obtained results, conclusions were made on the possibility of reducing residual SSS and deformation in structures with asymmetric reinforcement schemes using a matrix containing carbon nanoparticles.

Keywords: *composite materials, nanosized particles, nanomodification, deformations, residual deformations, residual stresses, SSS.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В работе исследуется влияние наномодификации углепластика на остаточное напряженно-деформированное состояние (НДС) после формования. Одним из способов снижения остаточных напряжений и деформаций является наномодификация. Основной задачей является определение степени влияния параметров наномодификации на остаточное НДС. В рамках данного исследования изготавливались 4 плиты. Две плиты выполнены из обычного связующего с укладкой $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$ и $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$ и две плиты из модифицированного связующего, с такой же структурой слоев. Для изготовленных пластин измерялись прогибы по каждой из четырех сторон, в ходе которого были получены остаточные деформации в панелях из наномодифицированного углепластика для рассматриваемых укладок с модифицированным связующим и без. Для анализа остаточного напряженного деформированного состояния проводился численный и аналитический расчет. Численный расчет проводился методом конечных элементов для случая, когда пластина закреплена в точке геометрического центра, силовая нагрузка отсутствует, температурная нагрузка – перепад 100°C. Аналитический расчет проводился для случая, когда пластина свободна от закрепления и внешней силовой нагрузки, температурная нагрузка – перепад на 100°C. В процессе исследования были получены варианты физико-механических свойств монослоя с использованием программы Digimat и метода осреднения Мори-Танак. Результаты, полученные аналитическим и численным методами, имеют хорошую корреляцию между собой, а в ходе сопоставления с экспериментом был определен метод расчета характеристик монослоя наиболее приближенный к экспериментальному результату. На основе полученных результатов были сделаны выводы о возможности снижения остаточного НДС и поводом в структурах с несимметричными схемами армирования при использовании матрицы содержащей углеродные наночастицы.

Ключевые слова: композитные материалы, наноразмерные частицы, наномодификация, поводки, остаточные деформации, остаточные напряжения, НДС.

1. INTRODUCTION

The paper investigates the effect of carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic nanomodification on the permanent stress-strain state (SSS) after molding. The creation of polymer composites based on nanomodified binders has long been one of the research priorities in the field of CM manufacturing technologies, and significant progress has been achieved in this area (Hsu and Herakovich, 1977; Zweben, 1977; Ditcher *et al.*, 1981; Manders and Bader, 1981; Christensen, 1982; Hucho *et al.*, 1994; Bakis *et al.*, 2002; Yerramalli and Waas, 2003; Gojny *et al.*, 2005; Fatykhov *et al.*, 2006; Stavichenko, 2007; Zhang

et al., 2007; Ma *et al.*, 2008; Zhang *et al.*, 2009; Jean *et al.*, 2011; Dong and Davies, 2012; Gururaja and Hari Rao, 2012; Raghavulu Thirumalai *et al.*, 2013; Afanasiev *et al.*, 2014; Sathishkumar *et al.*, 2014; Harik, 2014; Swolfs *et al.*, 2014; Jagannatha and Harish, 2015; O'Brien and Zagheri, 2018; Üstündağ *et al.*, 2019; Kurchatov *et al.*, 2019; Bulychev, 2019a; Bulychev, 2019b; Solyaev *et al.*, 2019; Babaytsev and Zotov, 2019). The development of CMs that improve their operational limits is based on reinforcing two or more fibers into a single polymer matrix, which leads to an improved material system called hybrid composites with a wide variety of material properties (Christensen, 1982). The study of the

mechanical characteristics of hybrid composites with glass fibers of $\pm 45^\circ$ and stainless steel $0^\circ/90^\circ$ is no less important when using similar structures (Gururaja and Hari Rao, 2012). In this study, hybrid and non-hybrid composites of various obstacles, fiber content, and weave types were fabricated and subjected to hysteretic tensile loads. The current state of hybrid composite materials, their technology, in terms of material properties, has an obvious advantage with an emphasis on various applications (Ditcher *et al.*, 1981).

As a rule, composites are molded at elevated temperatures, after which they are cooled to operating temperature. Due to the high anisotropy of the physicochemical properties during cooling, the composite layers shrink unevenly in thickness and direction (Stavichenko, 2007). This leads to the appearance of residual deflections and internal stresses in composite parts (Hsu and Herakovich, 1977; Ditcher *et al.*, 1981; Fatykhov *et al.*, 2006; Stavichenko, 2007; Üstündağ *et al.*, 2019). One of the ways to reduce residual stresses and strains is nanomodification (Raghavalu Thirumalai *et al.*, 2013; Sathishkumar *et al.*, 2014; Kurchatov *et al.*, 2019; Bulychev, 2019a; Bulychev, 2019b; Solyaev *et al.*, 2019; Babaytsev and Zotov, 2019). The introduction of nanosized particles into the composition of the composite or its components (fiber or binder) allows not only to increase its physical and mechanical properties, but also to improve the picture of the residual stress-strain state.

The main task is to determine the degree of influence of the nanomodification parameters on the residual VAT.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To study the effect of carbon nanomodification, 4 plates were made, characterized by layering and a binder. Two plates are made of a conventional binder with laying $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$ and $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$, and two plates are of a modified binder with the same layer structure. For the manufactured plates, deflections were measured on each of the four sides, during which residual strains were obtained in the panels of nanomodified carbon fiber.

To analyze the residual stress-strain state, a numerical and analytical calculation was performed. Based on the simulation result, the result obtained was compared with each other and with the experiment for the corresponding version of the stacking under consideration.

The studies used fullerene black produced by "Nanopolimer" (Russia). This fullerene black without other additives contains 10% of C60 and C70 fullerenes and 100% carbon. The black density is 0.3 g/cm^3 . The carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic sample was made using EDT-10. Epoxy binder (Russia) and carbon fibers NTA-40 (Toho Tenax Co. Ltd.). Typical matrix properties are as follows: Young's modulus is 2–3 hPa, Poisson's constant is 0.35, and the ultimate stress is 20–25 MPa. In order to obtain nanomodified samples, a binder heated to 90°C without hardeners was added to fullerene black (0.2 wt.%). In the manufacture of samples, the matrix was mixed with a paddle mixer for 30 minutes, followed by ultrasonic dispersion for 5 minutes to reduce agglomeration.

For the experimental study, four plates were made: two plates with $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$ and $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$ with a modified binder and two plates with $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$ and $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$ with a conventional binder. Due to the high anisotropy during cooling after molding, internal stresses arose in the plates and, as a result, leashes. The resulting deflections of the plates were measured on each of the four sides, Figure 1. To measure the deflection of the plate, it was fixed on a flat surface at two extreme points, and the deflection was measured in the center of the side with a caliper. Table 1 presents the results of measurements of the deflections of the manufactured plate with the layer structure $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$ and with the layer structure $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$.

For analytical calculation, we considered a plate free from fastening and external power load, and the temperature load is a difference of 100°C .

Numerical calculation is carried out using the finite element method. The plate under consideration was fixed at the point of the geometric center, there was no power load, and the temperature load was a difference of 1000°C .

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. Numerical and analytical modeling of residual strains in panels with asymmetric styling

We will carry out numerical and analytical modeling of residual strains in panels with asymmetric styling. A multilayer panel of a polymer composite with anisotropy due to the non-symmetry of the properties of the structure of the package in thickness is considered. For the panel, we introduce the x, y, z coordinate system so that the x, y axes are centered around the reinforcement plane, and the z-axis is directed along with the panel thickness. Generally, six

internal force factors arise in the panel: $N_x, N_y, N_{xy}, M_x, M_y, M_{xy}$. Physical relations, in this case, will be the following (Equation 1).

Where $N_x^T, N_y^T, N_{xy}^T, N_x^H, N_y^H, N_{xy}^H$ – linear forces caused by thermal deformation (index T) and initial layers tension (index H); $M_x^T, M_y^T, M_{xy}^T, M_x^H, M_y^H, M_{xy}^H$ – linear moments caused by thermal deformation (index T) and initial layers tension (index H); B_{mn}, C_{mn}, D_{mn} – panel generalized rigidities ($m, n = 1, 2, 3$); $\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_{xy}$ – panel linear strains in the reference plane; $\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}$ – panel curvature in the reference plane.

The relation between the panel strains in the reference plane with displacements u_0, v_0 (Equation 2). Relationship between panel curvature and standard rotation angles θ_x, θ_y (Equation 3). The relationship between standard rotation angles with deflection w has the following form (Equation 4). Where ψ_x, ψ_y – lateral shears.

Panel generalized rigidities are defined as follows (Equations 5-8). Where e – reference plane coordinate (for an asymmetric panel is chosen arbitrarily); $m, n = 1, 2, 3, r = 0, 1, 2$. Formulae for the force and moment caused by temperature fields (Equations 9-10). Where (Equations 11-12): Z_k – coordinate of k layer, counted from the reference plane; N – number of layers; $b_{ij}^{(k)}$ – linear stiffness of k layer, referenced to the panel axes (x, y); ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$); ΔT – temperature drop due to cooling; $\alpha_1^{(k)}, \alpha_2^{(k)}, \alpha_3^{(k)}$ – coefficients of linear thermal expansion of k layer in the panel axes.

Similarly, we record the force and moment from the initial tension (Equations 13-14). Where (Equations 15-16): $\varepsilon_{H1}^{(k)}, \varepsilon_{H2}^{(k)}, \varepsilon_{H3}^{(k)}$ – initial layers' strains in the panel axes.

The linear stiffness for k layer in the case of an asymmetric panel are as follows (Equations 17-18). The coefficients of linear thermal expansion for k layer, as well as layer strains caused by the initial tension, in the panel axes, are determined by appropriate transformation (Equations 19-20). In the above formulae, $m^{(k)}$ and $n^{(k)}$ are the trigonometric functions of $\varphi^{(k)}$ layers' orientation angle relative to the x panel (Equation 21).

We will consider a flat panel without initial curvature with free of load and fixing edges, subject to the temperature field evenly distributed

over the thickness (Yerramalli and Waas, 2003; Raghavalu Thirumalai *et al.*, 2013; Sathishkumar *et al.*, 2014; Harik, 2014; Swolfs *et al.*, 2014). The reference surface coincides with the median surface. The orthotropic composite structure $B_{13} = B_{31} = 0$ and $C_{13}, C_{31}, C_{23}, C_{32}, D_{13}, D_{31}$ coefficients are small and can be neglected. Taking this into consideration, the physical relations for the orthotropic composite structure in the expanded form will look like (Equations 22-23).

Thus, in the case of the orthotropic composite structure, the determination of the deformed state splits into 2 independent problems of finding the deflections (curvature component κ_x, κ_y) and twist (κ_{xy}).

3.2. Determination of stress in layers using Hooke's law

Stresses in the layers are determined by Hooke's law using the curvature and deformation components obtained from (Equation 1), i.e. (Equations 24) (Harik, 2014; Sathishkumar *et al.*, 2014; Swolfs *et al.*, 2014; Babaytsev and Zotov, 2019; Bulychev, 2019b). In this case, z_k is the coordinate of the layer's median surface, i.e., $z_k = (Z_k - e) - h_k/2$. To move to the $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}$ stresses in the layer axes, it is necessary to use the transformation formulae when turning the coordinate axes (Equation 25).

As it is evident from the physical relations (1) in multilayer panels with asymmetric lay-up, layers subject to tension-compression will cause the panel bending. Such complex behavior of panels in highly loaded structures can lead to a decrease in their efficiency. In addition, the molding of such panels will be accompanied by the permanent temperature flexural strains (buckling) (Hsu and Herakovitch, 1977; Ditcher *et al.*, 1981; Fatykhov *et al.*, 2006; Stavichenko, 2007; Üstündağ *et al.*, 2019).

Panels with a symmetrical layers' arrangement, i.e., when the same layer ($N-k$) corresponds to the layer (k), where N is the total number of layers in the panel. Taking this into account, we write the formulae for generalized stiffness in the following simplified form (Equation 26).

The Z_k coordinate is then counted from the $e=h/2$ medial plane, and the sum is calculated only by half the panel. The physical relations (Equation 1) for an orthotropic panel with load-free edges will then take such a form (Equations 27-28). From (Equation 28), it is easy to see that the molding of flat panels with a symmetrical panel structure will

not lead to their buckling.

As a result of the study, we can distinguish the algorithm in the analytical analysis of the residual stress-strain state, conditionally divided into the main stages:

1. The calculation of the stiffness characteristics of the package according to Equations 5, 17-21;

2. Determination of internal force factors caused by the initial tension and temperature difference according to Equations 23-26;

3. Determination of the components of deformations and curvature from physical relations (Equation 1);

4. Calculation of stresses in composite layers using Hooke's law (Equations 24, 25).

As the calculated characteristics of the monolayer used in the simulation, the values obtained from the assumption that the reinforcing particles of fullerene soot are absolutely solid and not destroyed, and at the same time have the shape of a sphere, are used. Therefore, a spherical inclusion model was used to model the properties of the filled matrix using the Digimat-MF program using the Mori-Tanaka averaging method (Zweben, 1977; Ditcher *et al.*, 1981; Christensen, 1982; Hucho *et al.*, 1994; Gojny *et al.*, 2005; Stavichenko, 2007; Jean *et al.*, 2011; Gururaja and Hari Rao, 2012; Jagannatha and Harish, 2015). The calculation was carried out with the effective volume content (volume content of the filler + volume content of the interfacial layer, under the assumption that their properties are equal). The effective volumetric content was selected, taking into account the results obtained at the test entrance: 1) in terms of tensile strength; 2) in modulus. In the course of this, the value of the average Young's modulus of the packet was obtained, but it differs from the test. It is known that when using test data for unidirectional material in the calculation of the properties of a layered package, errors can occur. Therefore, it is usually necessary to use the stiffness data of several package options with different layer stackings (Bulychev, 2019b). In this work, for the properties of a monolayer, we will use an overestimated value of the transverse modulus equal to 28 GPa, which is more than the experimental data obtained on unidirectional samples (6.5 GPa). In this case, it is possible to reliably describe the obtained experimental data on the Young's modulus of the composite samples with symmetric stacking $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$ (Manders and Bader, 1981; Ditcher *et al.*, 1981; Christensen, 1982; Bakis *et al.*, 2002; Ma *et*

al., 2008; Gururaja and Hari Rao, 2012; Afanasiev *et al.*, 2014; O'Brien and Zaghi, 2018).

For numerical and analytical calculations, the calculation was carried out for four variants of the physicomaterial characteristics of the monolayer taking into account two stacking options using the properties of a monolayer of pure carbon fiber and nanomodified carbon fiber, Table 2. A total of 8 calculations were performed for the stacking option $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$, the calculation results of deflections are presented in Table 3 and 8 of the calculations for $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$, the calculation results of the deflections are presented in Table 4.

The results of the distribution of normal stresses between the layers for laying $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$ and $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$ are given in Figure 2. The results obtained by analytical and numerical methods are the same. However, the greatest similarity with experimental data is provided by 4 methods for determining the effective properties of a monolayer. The residual deformations and stresses for laying $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$ are 25-46% higher than in laying $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$. At the same time, nanomodified composites, to a greater extent, reduce residual strains and stresses for laying $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$, about 26%.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

Investigation of the residual stress-strain state of structural elements made of carbon fiber reinforced plastic using the values of thermoelastic characteristics of composite monolayers identified on the basis of the developed methods revealed the possibility of reducing the residual SSS and leach in structures with asymmetric reinforcement schemes using a matrix containing carbon nanoparticles.

The results obtained by analytical and numerical methods are identical. The most similar to experimental data is the fourth method for determining the effective properties of a monolayer. This method is a model of spherical inclusions for modeling the properties of a filled matrix using the Digimat-MF program and the Mori-Tanaka averaging method taking into account the results of physical and mechanical tests.

Using the proposed model of thermoelasticity of the layered composite, it was also found that the addition of nanoparticles within the range recommended by the standard range of 10% only leads to a slight increase in the longitudinal elastic modulus and the shear modulus of the monolayer.

The obtained result showed the possibility of improving the mechanical properties of carbon fiber samples with a nanomodified binder, as well as the possibility of taking into account the effect of carbon nanomodification on the residual stress-strain state (SSS) after molding. The process of further reducing residual deformations and stresses by adding nanosized particles to the composition of the composite or its components (fiber or binder) takes place. However, this process is non-linear and requires further investigation, taking into account the models used to calculate the results obtained.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS:

The work was carried out with the financial support of the state project of the Ministry of Education and Science project code 9.9074.2017/BCh.

6. REFERENCES:

- Afanasiev, A.V., Nguen, D.Q., Solyaev, Y.O., Dudchenko, A.A. *Nanomechanics Science and Technology: An International Journal*, **2014**, 5(3), 229-238.
- Babaytsev, A.V., Zotov, A.A. *Russian Metallurgy (Metally)*, **2019**, 13(1), 1452-1455, DOI: 10.1134/S0036029519130020
- Bakis, C.E., Bank, L.C., Brown, V.L., Cosenza, E., Davalos, J.F., Lesko, J.J., Machida, A., Rizkalla, S.H., Triantafillou, T.C., *Journal of Composites Constructions*, **2002**, 6(2), 73-87.
- Bulychev, N.A. *Bulletin of the Lebedev Physics Institute*, **2019a**, 46(7), 219-221.
- Bulychev, N.A. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, **2019b**, 44(57), 29933-29936.
- Christensen, R.M. *Mechanics of composite materials*. New York: A. Wiley-Interscience Publication John Wiley&Sons, **1982**.
- Ditcher, K., Rhodes, F.E., Webber, J.P.H. *Journal of Strain Analysis*, **1981**, 16, 43-51.
- Dong, Ch., Davies, I.J. *Materials and Design*, **2012**, 37, 450-457.
- Fatykhov, M.A., Enikeev, T.I., Akimov, I.A. *Bulletin of OSU*, **2006**, 2(2), 87-92.
- Gojny, F.H., Wichmann, M.H.G., Fiedler, B.K., Schulte, K. *Composites Science and Technology*, **2005**, 65, 2300-2313.
- Gururaja, M.N., Hari Rao, A.N. *International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering*, **2012**, 1(6), 352-355.
- Harik, V. *Trends in Nanoscale Mechanics: Mechanics of Carbon Nanotubes, Graphene, Nanocomposites and Molecular Dynamics*. Berlin: Springer, **2014**.
- Hsu, P.W., Herakovich, C.T. *Composite Materials*, **1977**, 5, 442-428.
- Hucho, C., Kraus, M., Maurer, D., Müller, V., Werner, H., Wohlers, M., Schlögl, R. *Molecular Crystals and Liquid Crystals*, **1994**, 245(1), 277-282.
- Jagannatha, T.D., Harish, G. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics Research*, **2015**, 4(2), 131-137.
- Jean, A., Willot, F., Cantournet, S., Forest, S., Jeulin, D. *International Journal for Multiscale Computational Engineering*, **2011**, 9(3), 271-303.
- Kurchatov, I.S., Bulychev, N.A., Kolesnik, S.A. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, **2019**, 8(3), 8328-8330.
- Ma, C., Ji, L.J., Zhang, R.P., Zhu, Y.F., Zhang, W., Koratkar, N. *Carbon*, **2008**, 46, 706-710.
- Manders, P.W., Bader, M.G. *Journal of Materials Science*, **1981**, 16, 2233-2245.
- O'Brien, C., Zaghi, A.E., Mechanical Characteristics of Hybrid Composites with $\pm 45^\circ$ Glass and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ Stainless Steel Fibers. University of Connecticut. Materials (Basel), **2018**, 4;11(8), Article number E1355.
- Raghavalu Thirumalai, D.P., Andersen, T.L., Markussen, Ch.M., Madsen B., Lilholt H. Tensile and compression properties of hybrid composites – A comparative study. *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM19) (pp. 1029-1035)*. Canadian Association for Composite Structures and Materials, Montréal, Canada, **2013**.
- Sathishkumar, T.P., Naveen, J., Satheeshkumar, S. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **2014**, 33(5), 454-471.
- Solyaev, Y., Lurie, S., Koshurina, A., Dobryanskiy, V., Kachanov, M. *International Journal of Engineering Science*, **2019**, 134, 66-76.
- Stavichenko, V.G. *Technological Systems*, **2007**, 4, 7-11.

25. Swolfs, Y., Gorbatiikh, L., Verpoest, I. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **2014**, 67, 181-200.
26. Üstündağ, O., Gook, S., Gumenyuk, A., Rethmeier, M. *Procedia Manufacturing*, **2019**, 36, 112-120.
27. Yerramalli, C.S., Waas, A.M. Compressive behavior of hybrid composites. *Proceedings of 44th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, Norfolk, Virginia, **2003**.
28. Zhang, W., Picu, R.C, Koratkar, N., *Journal of Applied Physics*, **2007**, 91(19), 193-109.
29. Zhang, W., Srivastava, I., Zhu, Y.F., Picu, R.C., Koratkar, N. *Small*, **2009**, 5(12), 1403–1407.
30. Zweben, C. *Journal of Materials Science*, **1977**, 12, 1325-1337.

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{13} & C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{23} & C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} \\ B_{31} & B_{32} & B_{33} & C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} \\ C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{13} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{23} \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & D_{31} & D_{32} & D_{33} \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} N_x^T \\ N_y^T \\ N_{xy}^T \\ M_x^T \\ M_y^T \\ M_{xy}^T \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} N_x^H \\ N_y^H \\ N_{xy}^H \\ M_x^H \\ M_y^H \\ M_{xy}^H \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x}; \varepsilon_y = \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y}; \varepsilon_{xy} = \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x}. \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$\kappa_x = \frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial x}; \kappa_y = \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial y}; \kappa_{xy} = \frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial x}. \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

$$\theta_x = \psi_x - \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}; \theta_y = \psi_y - \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}, \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

$$B_{mn} = I^{(0)}_{mn}, \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

$$C_{mn} = I^{(1)}_{mn} - eI^{(0)}_{mn}, \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

$$D_{mn} = I^{(2)}_{mn} - 2eI^{(1)}_{mn} + e^2I^{(0)}_{mn}, \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

$$I^{(r)}_{mn} = \int_0^h b_{mn} Z^r dt = \frac{1}{r+1} \sum_{k=1}^N b_{mn}^{(k)} (Z_k^{r+1} - Z_{k-1}^{r+1}), \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

$$N_x^T = \sum_{j=1}^3 N_{1j}^T, N_y^T = \sum_{j=1}^3 N_{2j}^T, N_{xy}^T = \sum_{j=1}^3 N_{3j}^T, \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

$$M_x^T = \sum_{j=1}^3 M_{1j}^T, M_y^T = \sum_{j=1}^3 M_{2j}^T, M_{xy}^T = \sum_{j=1}^3 M_{3j}^T, \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

$$N_{ij}^T = \Delta T \sum_{k=1}^N [b_{ij}^{(k)} \overline{\alpha_j^{(k)}} (Z_k - Z_{k-1})]; \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

$$M_{ij}^T = \Delta T \sum_{k=1}^N b_{ij}^{(k)} \overline{\alpha_j^{(k)}} \left[\frac{1}{2} (Z_k^2 - Z_{k-1}^2) - e(Z_k - Z_{k-1}) \right]; \quad (\text{Eq. 12})$$

$$N_x^H = \sum_{j=1}^3 N_{1j}^H, N_y^H = \sum_{j=1}^3 N_{2j}^H, N_{xy}^H = \sum_{j=1}^3 N_{3j}^H, \quad (\text{Eq. 13})$$

$$M_x^H = \sum_{j=1}^3 M_{1j}^H, M_y^H = \sum_{j=1}^3 M_{2j}^H, M_{xy}^H = \sum_{j=1}^3 M_{3j}^H, \quad (\text{Eq. 14})$$

$$N_{ij}^H = \sum_{k=1}^N [b_{ij}^{(k)} \overline{\varepsilon_{ij}^{(k)}} (Z_k - Z_{k-1})]; \quad (\text{Eq. 15})$$

$$M_{ij}^H = \sum_{k=1}^N b_{ij}^{(k)} \overline{\varepsilon_{ij}^{(k)}} \left[\frac{1}{2} (Z_k^2 - Z_{k-1}^2) - e(Z_k - Z_{k-1}) \right]; \quad (\text{Eq. 16})$$

$$\begin{aligned} b_{11}^{(k)} &= [\overline{E_1} m^4 + \overline{E_2} n^4 + 2(\overline{E_1} \nu_{12} + 2G_{12}) m^2 n^2]^{(k)} \\ b_{22}^{(k)} &= [\overline{E_1} n^4 + \overline{E_2} m^4 + 2(\overline{E_1} \nu_{12} + 2G_{12}) m^2 n^2]^{(k)} \\ b_{12}^{(k)} &= b_{21}^{(k)} = [\overline{E_1} \nu_{12} + [\overline{E_1} + \overline{E_2} - 2(\overline{E_1} \nu_{12} + 2G_{12})] m^2 n^2]^{(k)} \\ b_{13}^{(k)} &= b_{31}^{(k)} = [mn[\overline{E_1} m^2 - \overline{E_2} n^2 - (\overline{E_1} \nu_{12} + 2G_{12})(m^2 - n^2)]]^{(k)}, \\ b_{23}^{(k)} &= b_{32}^{(k)} = [mn[\overline{E_1} n^2 - \overline{E_2} m^2 + (\overline{E_1} \nu_{12} + 2G_{12})(m^2 - n^2)]]^{(k)} \\ b_{33}^{(k)} &= [(\overline{E_1} + \overline{E_2} - 2\overline{E_1} \nu_{12}) m^2 n^2 + G_{12} (m^2 - n^2)]^{(k)} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 17})$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_1^{(k)} &= \frac{E_1^{(k)}}{1 - \nu_{12}^{(k)} \nu_{21}^{(k)}}, \\ E_2^{(k)} &= \frac{E_2^{(k)}}{1 - \nu_{12}^{(k)} \nu_{21}^{(k)}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 18})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \overline{\alpha_1} \\ \overline{\alpha_2} \\ \overline{\alpha_3} \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} = \begin{pmatrix} m^2 & n^2 \\ n^2 & m^2 \\ 2mn & -2mn \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \end{pmatrix}^{(k)}, \quad (\text{Eq. 19})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \overline{\varepsilon_{H1}} \\ \overline{\varepsilon_{H2}} \\ \overline{\varepsilon_{H3}} \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} = \begin{pmatrix} m^2 \\ n^2 \\ 2mn \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} (\varepsilon_H)^{(k)}. \quad (\text{Eq. 20})$$

$$\begin{aligned} m^{(k)} &= \cos(\varphi^{(k)}), \\ n^{(k)} &= \sin(\varphi^{(k)}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 21})$$

$$\begin{cases} 0 = B_{11}\varepsilon_x + B_{12}\varepsilon_y + C_{11}\kappa_x + C_{12}\kappa_y - N_x^T - N_x^H \\ 0 = B_{12}\varepsilon_x + B_{22}\varepsilon_y + C_{21}\kappa_x + C_{22}\kappa_y - N_y^T - N_y^H \\ 0 = C_{11}\varepsilon_x + C_{12}\varepsilon_y + D_{11}\kappa_x + D_{12}\kappa_y - M_x^T - M_x^H \\ 0 = C_{21}\varepsilon_x + C_{22}\varepsilon_y + D_{21}\kappa_x + D_{22}\kappa_y - M_y^T - M_y^H \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 22})$$

$$\begin{cases} 0 = B_{33}\varepsilon_{xy} + C_{33}\kappa_{xy} - N_{xy}^T - N_{xy}^H \\ 0 = C_{33}\varepsilon_{xy} + D_{33}\kappa_{xy} - M_{xy}^T - M_{xy}^H \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 23})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & b_{13} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & b_{23} \\ b_{31} & b_{32} & b_{33} \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x + \kappa_x \cdot z_k - \overline{\alpha_1}^{(k)} \cdot \Delta T - \overline{\varepsilon_{H1}}^{(k)} \\ \varepsilon_y + \kappa_y \cdot z_k - \overline{\alpha_2}^{(k)} \cdot \Delta T - \overline{\varepsilon_{H2}}^{(k)} \\ \varepsilon_{xy} + \kappa_{xy} \cdot z_k - \overline{\alpha_3}^{(k)} \cdot \Delta T - \overline{\varepsilon_{H3}}^{(k)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{Eq. 24})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} = \begin{pmatrix} m^2 & n^2 & 2mn \\ n^2 & m^2 & -2mn \\ -mn & mn & (m^2 - n^2) \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix}^{(k)} \quad (\text{Eq. 25})$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_{mn} &= 2 \sum_{k=1}^{N/2} b_{mn}^{(k)} (Z_k - Z_{k-1}) \\ D_{mn} &= \frac{2}{3} \sum_{k=1}^{N/2} b_{mn}^{(k)} (Z_k^3 - Z_{k-1}^3) \\ C_{mn} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 26})$$

$$\begin{cases} 0 = B_{11}\varepsilon_x + B_{12}\varepsilon_y - N_x^t - N_x^H \\ 0 = B_{12}\varepsilon_x + B_{22}\varepsilon_y - N_y^t - N_y^H \\ 0 = D_{11}\kappa_x + D_{12}\kappa_y \\ 0 = D_{21}\kappa_x + D_{22}\kappa_y \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 27})$$

$$\begin{cases} 0 = B_{33}\varepsilon_{xy} - N_{xy}^t - N_{xy}^H \\ 0 = D_{33}\kappa_{xy} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 28})$$

Table 1. Comparison of deflections for lay-up $[0_{10} / 45_{10}]$ and lay-up $[0_{10} / 90_{10}]$ with and without nano

		Lay-up experiment $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$	Lay-up experiment $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$
Deflection on the long side, mm	With nano	5.85	4.35
	Without nano	5.95	3.2
Deflection on the short side, mm	With nano	4.1	2.1
	Without nano	3.7	2.75

Table 2. Material stress-strain properties

No.		E_{11} [MPa]	E_{22} [MPa]	G_{12} [MPa]	ν_{12}	α_{1b} [$10^{-6} K^{-1}$]	α_2, α_3 [$10^{-6} K^{-1}$]	G_{23} [MPa]
1	Carbon fiber-reinforced plastic	129960	7056	2658	0.593	0.7	42	2214
	Nanomodified carbon fiber-reinforced plastic	135130	19078	8225	0.567	3.4	44	6085
2	Carbon fiber-reinforced plastic	129510	5211	1917	0.596	0.46	42	1632
	Nanomodified carbon fiber-reinforced plastic	129760	6266	2337	0.594	0.6	42	1965
3	Carbon fiber-reinforced plastic	129500	4730	2050	0.29	0.19	20	1670
	Nanomodified carbon fiber-reinforced plastic	129750	5700	2500	0.29	0.26	20	2010
4	Carbon fiber-reinforced plastic	129500	4730	2050	0.29	-10.4	20	1670
	Nanomodified carbon fiber-reinforced plastic	129750	5700	2500	0.29	-12	20	2010

Table 3. Comparison of deflections for options 1-4 and lay-up $[0_{10} / 45_{10}]$ with experiment

		1	2	3	4	Experiment
Deflection on the long side, mm	With nano	10.6	6.6	3.2	5.1	4.35
	Without nano	7	5.3	2.8	4.3	3.2
Deflection on the short side, mm	With nano	5.7	3.5	1.7	2.8	2.1
	Without nano	3.8	2.8	1.5	2.3	2.75

Table 4. Comparison of deflections for options 1-4 and lay-up $[0_{10} / 90_{10}]$ with experiment

		1	2	3	4	Experiment
Deflection on the long side, mm	With nano	19.9	12.4	5.6	9.2	5.85
	Without nano	13.3	10	5	7.7	5.95
Deflection on the short side, mm	With nano	10.7	6.7	3	4.9	4.1
	Without nano	7.2	5.4	2.7	4.2	3.7

Figure 1. Measurement of the panel deflection using caliper rule

Figure 2. The results of the distribution of normal stresses between the layers for laying $[0_{10}/90_{10}]$: a, e – without nanoparticles; c, g – with nanoparticles and $[0_{10}/45_{10}]$: b, e – without nanoparticles, d, h – with nanoparticles (a, b, c, d – Distribution of normal stresses in the layers σ_1 , MPa; e, f, g, h – Distribution of normal stresses in the layers σ_2 , MPa)

INSTRUCTIONS FOR AUTHORS

We ask authors always to visit the online instructions for the use of the latest instructions available. Manuscripts must be submitted using the template available on the Journal's website.

PREPARATION OF MANUSCRIPTS

1. PREPARATION OF MANUSCRIPTS
 2. THE FIRST PAGE OF THE MATERIAL
 3. THE CENTRAL TEXT PART OF THE MATERIAL
 4. GUIDELINES FOR REFERENCES
 5. FIGURES
 6. TABLES
 7. MATHEMATICAL EXPRESSIONS
 8. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL
-

1. PREPARATION OF MANUSCRIPTS (TEMPLATE):

Please, observe the following points in preparing manuscripts. Papers not conforming strictly to these instructions may be returned to their authors for appropriate revision or may be delayed in the review process.

Readability: Manuscripts should be written in clear, concise, and grammatically correct English (British or American English throughout). The editors can not undertake wholesale revisions of poorly written papers. Every paper must be free of unnecessary jargon and readable by any specialist of the related field. The abstract should be written in an explanatory style that will be comprehensible also to readers who are not experts in the subject matter.

General format: The complete paper has to be written, preferably in Rich Text Format either in an MS-Word (.doc) or a Br.Office (.odt) compatible file. Page size: A4, margins: 2 cm on each side, line spacing: single, font type: Arial. Please leave headers and footers unchanged, since the editors should fill it. Please check guidelines for accurate information based on all different categories (review articles, technical notes, etc.) available. A single file of the whole manuscript should then be submitted through TQJ's email (journal.tq@gmail.com). The Journal no longer accepts submissions in any other form.

The order of the material should be as follows: Title, Author(s), Abstract, Keywords, Main text (Introduction, Review of Literature, Definitions (if any), Materials and Methods, Results, Discussion), Acknowledgements (if any), References, Appendix (if any). This structure of the main text is not obligatory, but the paper must be logically presented. Footnotes should be avoided. The main text must be written with font size 11, Arial, justify. Within each main section, three levels of subheadings are available, and the titles must be bold, bold, and italic, italic, respectively.

The manuscript should contain the whole text, figures, tables, and explanations according to the followings (we suggest using the template file):

2. THE FIRST PAGE OF THE MATERIAL SHOULD BE AS FOLLOWS:

Title: (both in Portuguese and English). The editors can provide the title in Portuguese for those whose Portuguese is not the first language. It should be brief and informative. The title should reflect

the essential aspects of the article, in a preferably concise form of not more than 100 characters and spaces. Font size 12, Arial, capital letters, center alignment.

By-line: Names (size 12, Arial, small capital) of the authors. No inclusion of scientific titles is necessary. In the case of two or more authors, place their names in the same row, separate them with a semicolon (;) and please indicate the corresponding author with * in superscript. The corresponding author should be the one submitting the article online and an e-mail given (only one e-mail) below the addresses of all authors. Authors from different institutions must be labeled with numbers in superscript after the names. Addresses of the authors, phone, and fax number should also be given (size 10). Authors should be grouped by address.

Abstract: (both in Portuguese and English). The editors can provide the translation of the abstract to Portuguese for those whose Portuguese is not the first language. Required for all manuscripts in which the problem, the principal results, and conclusions are summarized. The abstract must be self-explanatory, preferably typed in one paragraph, and limited to max. 200 words. It should not contain formulas, references, or abbreviations. The name ABSTRACT should be written in capital letters, Arial, size 12, bold, left alignment. The abstract should be written font Arial, size 10, justify.

Keywords: (both in Portuguese and English. The editors can provide the keywords in Portuguese for those who Portuguese is not the first language). Keywords should not exceed five, not including items appearing in the title. The keywords should be supplied, indicating the scope of the paper. Size 10, italic, justify, only the word Keywords must be bold, left alignment.

The authors should include Abbreviations and Nomenclature listings when necessary.

3. THE CENTRAL TEXT PART OF THE MATERIAL SHOULD BE AS FOLLOWS:

The words Introduction, Materials, and Methods, Results and Discussion, Conclusion, Acknowledgements, and References must be written in capital letters, Arial, font size 12, left alignment, bold.

Introduction: The introduction must clearly state the problem, the reason for doing the work, the hypotheses or theoretical predictions under consideration, and the essential background. It should not contain equations or mathematical notation. A brief survey of the relevant literature so that a non-specialist reader could understand the significance of the presented results.

Materials and Methods: Provide sufficient details to permit repetition of the experimental work. The technical description of methods should be given when such methods are new.

Results and Discussion: Results should be presented concisely. Also, point out the significance of the results and place the results in the context of other work and theoretical background.

Conclusion: Summarize the data discussed in the Results and Discussion showing the relevance of the work and how different it is from other researches. Also, point out the benefits and improvements that can be observed to develop new scientific standards that can change something in the related field.

Acknowledgments: (if any) These should be placed in a separate paragraph at the end of the text, immediately before the list of references. It may include funding information too.

References: In the text, references should be cited in Harvard style (Author, year). Alternatively, the author's surname may be integrated into the text, followed by the year of publication in parentheses. Cite only essential resources, avoid citing unpublished material. References to papers "in press" must mean that the article has been accepted for publication, at the end of the paper list references alphabetically by the last name of the first author. Please, list only those references that are cited in the text and prepare this list as an automatically numbered list. The word References with size 12, Arial,

bold, capital letters, left alignment.

4. GUIDELINES FOR REFERENCES:

- The Journal uses the APA (American Psychological Association) FORMAT CITATION as follows:

Author's surname, initial(s). (Date Published). **Title of Source.** **Location of publisher: publisher.** Retrieved from URL

Author Rules:

1. **Initials are separated and ended by a period.**

Examples: Goldani, E.
De Boni, L.A.B.

2. **Multiple authors are separated by commas and an ampersand.**

Examples: Goldani, E. & De Boni, L.A.B.
Goldani, E., De Boni, L.A.B. & Casanova, K.

3. **Multiple authors with the same surname and initial: add their name in square brackets.**

Example: Goldani, E. [Eduardo]

Date Rules:

1. **Date refers to date of publishing**
2. **If the date is unknown 'n.d' is used in its place.**

Example: De Boni, L.A.B (n.d)

Title Rules:

1. **The format of this changes depending on what is being referenced**

Publisher Rules:

1. **If in the US: the city and two letter state code must be stated.**

Examples: San Diego, CA
Houston, TX
New York, NY

2. **If not in the US: the city and country must be stated.**

Examples: Sydney, Australia
Lisbon, Portugal
Rome, Italy

Retrieved from URL: This is used if the source is an online source

- ✓ **The Journal recommend to visit the websites below for a more detailed information.**

< <https://www.mendeley.com/guides/apa-citation-guide> >
< <https://libguides.murdoch.edu.au/APA6/all> >
< <https://aut.ac.nz.libguides.com/APA6th/referencelist> >

5. FIGURES:

The number of pictures (including graphs, diagrams, etc.) should not exceed 10 and should be submitted either in JPG or PNG formats. All photographs, charts, and diagrams should be numbered consecutively (e.g., Figure 1) in the order in which they are referred in the text. Caption must appear below the figure (size 11, bold, italic) and should be sufficiently detailed to enable us to understand apart from the text. Explanation of lettering and symbols should be also given in the caption and only exceptionally in the figures. Figures should be of good quality and preferably in black and white. (Color figures will appear in the downloadable files, but all papers will be printed in black and white.) Scanned figures should be at a resolution of 800 dpi/bitmap for line graphs. Diagrams containing chemical structures should be of high graphical quality and always be of the same size so that they can be uniformly reduced. Figures should have a maximum width of one Journal column (8.5 cm) to be inserted on the body of the text so that they can be applied to the standards of the Journal. If the figures exceed 8.5 cm, they will be placed at the end of the article. Also, authors may be requested to submit each figure also as an image file in one of the following formats: jpg or png. For pictures, graphs, diagrams, tables, etc., identical to material already published in the literature, authors should seek permission for publication from the companies or scientific societies holding the copyrights and send it to the editors of TQ along with the final form of the manuscript.

6. TABLES:

Tables should be self-explanatory. They should be mentioned in the text, numbered consecutively (e.g., Table 1) and accompanied by title at the top (size 11, bold, italic). Please insert all the tables in the text, do not enclose huge tables which cannot be fit within the page margins.

7. MATHEMATICAL EXPRESSIONS:

In general, minimize unusual typographical requirements, use solidus, built-up fractions. Avoid lengthy equations that will take several lines (possibly by defining terms of the equation in separate displays). For drawing equations, please use the Equation Editor of Word, if possible. Make subscripts and superscripts clear. Display only those mathematical expressions that must be numbered for later reference or that need to be emphasized. Number displayed equations consecutively throughout the paper. The numbers should be placed in parentheses to the right of the equation, e.g. (Eq. 1).

8. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL:

Any Supplementary material (other figures, tables, diagrams, etc.) should be placed at the end of the manuscript and indicated as such. A single.PDF - document, including the supplementary material, should be submitted.

Editors, at any time of the editing process, may ask authors to split off part of the manuscript, presenting it as supplementary material.

PAGE CHARGES (1), DISCOUNTS (2), AND FREE PUBLICATION OPPORTUNITIES (3)

Authors are required to pay a publication fee to share in the costs of production. The fee will be asked if and when the article is accepted for publication. Once full payment has been made (PayPal, Bank Transfer, or Western Union Services), the paper will be published at the Ahead of Print and scheduled for the next available issue. All waivers (as well as the publication fee requests) are applied to the accepted papers after successful peer-review only.

Please observe the flowchart below to understand how we work.

1. PAGE CHARGES PRICES:

*Brazilian authors, USD 110

*Other countries income groups:

High income (or nuclear-capable countries) - USD 300

Upper middle-income USD 250

Lower middle-income USD 120

Lower middle income (Heavily indebted poor countries (HIPC)) USD 100

Low-income USD 100

Low income (Heavily indebted poor countries (HIPC)) USD 80

(*) Classification according to the World Bank list of economies (June 2017)

** Optional page formatting fee + USD 80. If you don't have time or the proper conditions to execute the formatting of your manuscript, we will find someone to do it for you.

2. ADDITIONAL FEES FOR PUBLICATION

a) Proofreading and / or plagiarism

If the submitted manuscript has more than 100 grammatical errors or plagiarism greater than 5%, a fee of USD 200 will be charged. This fee does not guarantee publication of the manuscript and is non-refundable.

b) Alteration of PDF files

After undergoing the final check of the manuscript file and Pre-Print PDF generation, a USD 100 will be charged with the authors in case they want to change something. For each new change, the fee is charged again.

If there is no need, additional fees are not charged.

3. DISCOUNTS

a) **50% discount** for authors who support other journals from the team (*Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry* (this is a 100% free journal)), with 1 manuscript approved for publication;

b) **100% discount** for authors who support other journals from the team (*Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry* (this is a 100% free journal)), with 2 manuscripts approved for publication;

c) **Volume discount**, if you are an author/collaborator of the journal, that has published with us 4 manuscripts (paid your full corresponded price), your fifth manuscript will be free of charge. Later the counting cycle restart.

4. FREE PUBLICATION:

a) Young scientists publishing the first manuscript of their career with us. Requirements: Copy of the curriculum with no publications; maximum of 2 authors; join the author alliance program (free).

b) All personal related to the production of the journals, from Brazil and abroad;

c) Long-time collaborators. Authors that have been publishing with us over the last decade, for more than 4 times, will pay no fees. Thank you for working with us for all those years.

d) Paper considered by the Editors of high quality, priority, and relevance for the development of the society shall pay no fees. Note that this condition is a small recognition prize, not something that you may request. Thank you for your comprehension.